

POINT CLOUD ATTRIBUTE COMPRESSION VIA NEURAL IMPLICIT REPRESENTATIONS

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Compression via neural networks

- There is a growing interest in exploiting **deep neural networks for signal compression**
 - ✓ For video compression, Google's VCT outperformed HEVC "very slow"

F. Mentzer et al., "VCT: a video compression transformer", arXiv, June 2022

- **Existing end-to-end** signal compression schemes are based on a universal autoencoder-like structure.

Implicit Neural Networks

- We investigate a different type of networks in the context of signal compression: **implicit neural representations**.
- They take as input a single coordinate from the signal domain and return the value of the signal at that coordinate
- They can represent **arbitrary continuous functions**
- In training, **the network overfits the signal** we want to represent
- In 3D rendering problems, neural implicit representations showed great capabilities in fitting **high-frequency components** of the signals.

$$(x, y) \rightarrow f(x, y)$$

Implicit Neural Networks

- A **multilayer perceptron** where the **input is a real-valued coordinate** x from the domain of the function and the output is the corresponding value of the function $f(x)$.
- Recently **sinusoidal activation functions** [1] or Fourier embeddings [2] have been proven to improve performance allowing to fit the high frequency components
- This paper is focused on using the recently proposed **SIRENs** [1], which are an MLP with sinusoidal activation functions.

[1] Vincent Sitzmann et al., "Implicit Neural Representations with Periodic Activation Functions", Proc. Neurips 2020

[2] Matthew Tancik et al., "Fourier Features Let Networks Learn High Frequency Functions in Low Dimensional Domains", Proc. Neurips 2020.

Proposed approach

- We present **NIC (Neural Implicit Compression)**: a novel paradigm for signal compression with neural networks where **the compact representation** of the signal **is** defined by **the very weights of the network**.
- Key concept: **efficient coding of the weights** → the rate depends entirely on that
- This is a preliminary exploration of this new compression paradigm

NIC paradigm – basic idea

- **Input:** signal $f(x)$ defined over coordinates x
- **Architecture:** a SIREN network (multilayer perceptron) with sinusoidal activation functions and a given number of layers/parameters: $NN_{\theta}(x)$
- **Training:**
 - Use the available samples $f(x_i)$ on a discretized grid x_i
 - Training set - **Data** are coordinates x_i ; **labels** are values $f(x_i)$
 - Training: employs backpropagation algorithm with MSE loss to compute **parameters** θ , imposing that the network yields $f(x_i)$ when queried with x_i
- **Encoding:** train network using $f(x)$ to obtain θ ; encode θ at desired rate
- **Decoding:** query $NN_{\theta}(x)$ with all coordinates of interest to obtain corresponding $f(x)$

NIC paradigm

NIC vs Autoencoders:

- **One** network **for** each specific **signal**
- The **network parameters** themselves represent **the signal**
- **Enc:** $(x, f(x)) \rightarrow NN_{\theta}(x)$
Dec: $\forall x, NN_{\theta}(x) \rightarrow f(x)$

- The encoder/decoder networks are **universal**
- The **network output** is the signal representation
- **Enc:** $f(x) \rightarrow NN_{\theta'}^E(x)$
Dec: $NN_{\theta''}^D(NN_{\theta'}^E(x)) = f(x)$

- ✓ NIC has potential advantages in **optimizing the representation for the specific signal**
- ✓ It does not rely on a training dataset that may or may not be representative of the signals to be compressed
- ✓ Coordinate-based MLPs simplify some challenging compression tasks (ex. point clouds irregular domains)
- ✓ This representation may be used for other tasks (e.g., superresolution)

Connections with transform coding

- A **two-layer SIREN** with N hidden features is equivalent to an **N -point 1D-DCT**:
 - Given an input scalar coordinate x , the output y of the two-layer SIREN is:

$$y = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} w_k^{(2)} \sin \left(w_k^{(1)} x + b_k^{(1)} \right) + b_k^{(2)}$$

Hypotheses: the input is sampled on a regular grid, the MSE is the loss function.

- The global minimum is reached when **the network converges to the inverse of the N point 1D-DCT**:

$$y_n = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \hat{y}_k \cos \left(\frac{\pi}{N} k \left(n + \frac{1}{2} \right) \right) \text{ with } 0 \leq n \leq N,$$

where \hat{y}_k is the k -th DCT coefficient of the signal y .

The network reaches the minimum when $w_k^{(2)} = \hat{y}_k$, $w_k^{(1)} = \frac{\pi}{N} k$, $b_k^{(1)} = \frac{\pi}{2N} k + \frac{\pi}{2}$

and $b_k^{(2)} = 0$.

Interpretation of SIREN

- A **two-layer SIREN** with N hidden features is equivalent to an **N -point 1D-DCT**.

- Interpretation:

- The **first layer acts a basis function generator**,
- The **last layer learns how to combine the basis functions** with suitable weights akin to transform-domain coefficients

- Notice that this is only a loose interpretation of what happens when deeper networks having fewer features are used.

Using Meta Learning

- Neural implicit representations can learn any signal but do not have any prior knowledge about data properties → **meta-learning methods**.
- Meta-learning: exploit **previously gained experience** over a task to improve future learning performance → train with few samples.
 - ✓ A first meta-learning training to find **good initialization point**.
 - ✓ **Innovative compression methodology**: **compress the difference** between the final weights of the network and their meta-learned initialization → improve the rate-distortion efficiency
- This achieve **significant rate savings** because the meta-learned initialization is a strong predictor of the final weights values.

NIC for point cloud color compression

1. Chosen **architecture**:
 - SIREN
 - 60, 80, 130 and 170 features per layer, with 5, 7 or 9 hidden layers
2. **Train** the network by minimizing the MSE.
3. **Compactly represent** the weights of the network:
 - Uniform scalar quantizer with quantization step sizes corresponding to a number of levels from 2^2 to 2^{12}
4. Use an **arithmetic entropy encoder** to represent the weights

NIC for point cloud color compression

- As an **example of application**, we evaluate the performance of the NIC paradigm for point cloud attribute compression.
- The implicit neural network takes as input the 3D coordinates of a point cloud and provides as output the corresponding RGB values.
 - ✓ 5, 7, or 9 layers
 - ✓ 60, 80, 130 or 170 parameters per layer
 - ✓ Scalar uniform quantization using from 2 to 12 bits per parameter
 - ✓ Arithmetic coding to represent the quantized weights
- The **proposed method** is compared to the latest version of **MPEG G-PCC** standard and with the **Region-Adaptive Hierarchical Transform** (RAHT)[3].
- Dataset: 4 point clouds from 8i Voxelized Full Bodies dataset (about 1M points)

Point cloud color compression

(a) Loot

(b) Longdress

Point cloud color compression

(c) Redandblack

(d) Soldier

Differential meta-learning

- The **proposed method with differential compression** is compared to a network **with meta-learned initialization and classic compression** (compression of the final values of the weights) and to a network **with random initialization and classic compression**.

(c) Redandblack

Conclusion and future directions

- We introduced a **novel NIC paradigm for signal compression**.
- The method shows **promising results**, yet the work is still in the early stages.
 - It can be seen as an extension of the DCT
 - May be used to implement other non-linear transforms
- There are several **open questions** that can open multiple lines of research for this topic.
 - Optimal activation functions
 - Quantization
 - Meta-learning
 - How to extend the method to image compression